

DECOMPOSITION OF POTASSIUM NITRATE IN SUNLIGHT.

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The photodecomposition of potassium nitrate in aqueous solution has been shown to occur in sunlight filtered through pyrex glass. The results are discussed in relation to the absorption spectrum of nitrates.

It has been noticed by many investigators that potassium nitrate decomposes in dilute aqueous solution when exposed to ultraviolet light yielding potassium nitrite and oxygen. The reaction is a complex one and is influenced by a variety of factors. Warburg (*Sitzungsber. preuss. Akad. Wiss.*, 1918, 1228) found that in polychromatic ultraviolet light, the photolysis occurs more rapidly in alkaline than in neutral or acid solutions. Warburg also studied the photochemical yield of nitrite in alkaline solution in ultraviolet light of wave-lengths 2070, 2530 and 2820Å. The quantum yield was in all cases much less than unity, increasing with increasing concentration and decreasing with increasing wave-length. Warburg suggested the hypothesis of a primary dissociation of the nitrate molecule when the energy of the absorbed quantum is sufficiently large but ascribed the low quantum yields to loss of energy by "damping" during absorption, the energy being shared with solvent molecules.

Anderson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 797) criticised the work of Warburg and stated that the photolysis of nitrate is a reversible reaction and soon attains a photostationary state after a small amount of nitrite has been formed. Villars (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 49, 326) denied the existence of a photostationary state and ascribed the results of Anderson to a faulty analytical method. Villars also determined the effect of hydrogen-ion concentration on the quantum yield, a variable which Warburg had indicated as existing. Using a light of wave-length of 2540Å, Villars showed that from p_H 6 to p_H 10 the quantum yield rose from 0.1 to 0.3 and was reasonably constant beyond this p_H . He also showed, in agreement with Warburg, that with increasing wave-length of light beyond 2540Å, the quantum yield at p_H 9.9 steadily fell. At 2700Å, the value was 0.07; at 3020Å, 0.013 and at 3660Å, 0.0.

The absorption spectra of nitrates have been studied by Halban, Scheibe, Morton, Maslakowicz and others ("Handbuck der Physik", 21, 329-31). For inorganic nitrates of lithium, sodium, potassium, ammonium, calcium, strontium, barium and magnesium the spectra have been studied in aqueous solutions of various concentrations. For concentrated solutions, the positions

of the absorption bands and also their intensities vary with the nature of the salt and its concentration. But for dilute solutions the absorption spectra are identical for all the salts. Evidently in dilute solution, where electrolytic dissociation is fairly complete, we are dealing with the absorption of the characteristic NO_3' ion. The absorption spectrum consists of two bands separated by a region of more or less free transmission; the first band extends from about $3500\text{\AA}$ to $2600\text{\AA}$ with its maximum at about $3000\text{\AA}$; the other band, which is much more intense, begins at about $2300\text{\AA}$ and has its maximum at about $2000\text{\AA}$. There is relatively feeble absorption beginning at about $2800\text{\AA}$. Recently Krishnan and Guha (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1934, 8A, 242) have ascribed the absorption bands to the photodissociation of the molecule of nitrate, following the work of Victor Henri on predissociation spectra. From the following table in which the heats of formation, in very dilute solutions, of some nitrates are listed ("International Critical Tables", Vol. 5) it will be seen that the difference between the values for the NO_3' and NO_2' ions is 101 kilojoules or 24 kilocalories and is constant for any nitrate and the corresponding nitrite.

	Na'	K'	NH_4'	Ha''
NO_3'	449'2	460'8	340'9	956'0
NO_2'	348'0	359'0	240'6	753'0
Difference	101	102	100'3	$2 \times 101'5$

We can, therefore, write the thermochemical relation

Krishnan and Guha (*loc. cit.*) suggest that the absorption, which begins at about $3500\text{\AA}$, is due to the photodissociation of the NO_3' ion to NO_2' ion and an O atom in the ground state (3p). We therefore obtain the relation

From (1) and (2) we obtain

i.e., the energy required to dissociate an oxygen molecule into two normal oxygen atoms is 114 kilocal. per gram mol. This value is in fair agreement with the values of 114'6 and 115'4 obtained by Henri from the predissociation limits of NO_2 and SO_2 molecules respectively.

The second absorption band which begins at about $2300\text{\AA}$ is ascribed to the following photodissociation

From the above considerations, it is possible to obtain dissociation of the potassium nitrate into nitrite in the regions of the two absorption bands. Warburg showed that photodecomposition occurs in the wave-lengths $2070\text{\AA}$, $2530\text{\AA}$ and $2820\text{\AA}$. As for the photochemical action of the second absorption band beginning at $3500\text{\AA}$, the data available are meagre.

DECOMPOSITION OF POTASSIUM NITRATE IN SUNLIGHT 231

Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 926) reported slight decomposition of nitrate under the influence of sunlight.

It is felt by us that it is necessary to establish by careful investigation whether the absorpctor band on the long wave limit is photochemically active or not. In the present investigation we have studied, under different conditions, the decomposition of potassium nitrate in pyrex flasks exposed to sunlight in which wave-lengths shorter than 2900Å are absent. The transmission of pyrex glass is given below as taken from International Critical Tables, II, 106.

Transmission factor (A) for laboratory pyrex glass.

Thickness=1 mm.

$\lambda =$ (I/I_0)	3960Å	3840Å	3610Å	3470Å	3300Å	3090Å	2800Å
	1'00	0'97	0'93	0'85	0'70	0'50	0'05

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

In this investigation Kahlbaum's potassium nitrate (Analytical Reagent) was used. The various solutions were made up with water redistilled in a quartz still and stored in pyrex or Jena bottles. 40 ml. of nitrate solutions were exposed to sunlight in pyrex conical flasks* of capacity 100 ml. and closed with corks. From time to time an aliquot portion of the solution was withdrawn and the nitrite formed by decomposition was estimated by the colorimetric method of Griess-Ilosvay. Due precautions were taken that the chemicals and water used in the course of estimation are free from nitrite as shown by the failure to respond to the Griess-Ilosvay test. The experiments were conducted in September-November.

TABLE I.

Influence of concentration.

Conc. of KNO_3 .	Nitrite-nitrogen per litre.			
	25 hrs.	50 hrs.	75 hrs.	100 hrs.
2'0M	1'21 mg.	2'24 mg.	3'85 mg.	5'53 mg.
1'0	1'19	1'92	3'82	5'50
0'5	1'13	1'60	2'80	4'38
0'1	0'50	0'84	1'66	2'19
0'05	0'39	0'76	1'12	1'72
0'005	0'15	—	0'73	1'14
0'0025	0'074	—	0'42	—

* Flasks containing potassium nitrate solutions, identical to those exposed to sunlight, were kept in the dark to serve as blanks. No nitrite was detected in any of these flasks in the time intervals stated.

TABLE II.
Influence of p_H .
 $KNO_3 = 0.5 M.$

Conc of KNO_3 .	Nitrite nitrogen per litre.			
	25 hrs.	50 hrs.	75 hrs.	100 hrs
7.0 mol.	0.9 mg.	1.16 mg.	2.08 mg.	2.95 mg
7.58	1.40	2.67	3.54	3.90
8.09	1.75	3.11	5.20	6.59
8.61	2.20	3.81	5.25	6.72
9.08	2.64	4.75	7.39	8.00
10.20	2.52	3.86	6.66	7.00
10.80	4.48	6.42	11.80	13.80
11.20	6.27	9.79	16.15	22.60
11.60	8.00	14.97	28.00	36.10
12.00	11.05	18.67	28.75	50.00

From the results in Table I it is evident that the decomposition of nitrate takes place in sunlight filtered through pyrex glass; with increase in the time of exposure there is an increase in the amount of nitrite obtained. Moreover, it is seen that the rate of decomposition decreases on lowering the concentration of nitrate. From Table II it will be seen that the p_H of the solution has a profound influence on the rate of decomposition, the higher the p_H , the higher is the rate of decomposition. The p_H indicated in the table can only be approximate as the experimental solutions were kept up for many weeks without any special precautions for preventing access of carbon dioxide of the atmosphere. The experimental solution in each case was made up by adding 87.5 ml. of a buffer solution of known p_H to 12.5 ml. of 4M-potassium nitrate solution freshly prepared. For p_H 7.58 to 9.08 Sørensen's borate-hydrochloric acid mixtures (*cf.* Clarke, "Determination of Hydrogen Ion Concentration", 1928, p. 209), for p_H 10.2 to 10.8 soda-borax buffers of Kolthoff and Vlesschouwer (p. 215) and for p_H 11.2 to 12.0 alkaliine phosphate buffers of Kolthoff and Vlesschouwer (p. 216) were employed.

It is thus clear from our results that potassium nitrate undergoes decomposition in sunlight filtered through pyrex glass. When we take into account the spectral distribution of solar radiation and the transmission of pyrex glass we can conclude that the decomposition occurs in radiation of wave-length longer than $2900\text{\AA}$.

Further work is in progress.